

BAD BANK : AN OUTLINE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

India's economic survey recommended creating a public sector asset rehabilitation agency in 2017, which is when the concept of establishing a bad bank in India was first proposed. The significance of the idea increased as a result of the rising issue of non-performing assets. The financial catastrophe experienced during the COVID-19 epidemic, which was essentially a bad bank idea developed by the USA in the late 1980s, becomes an essential component. It was anticipated that the bad bank would assist conventional banks by acquiring their hazardous assets, typically for less than the book value of the loans, and handling them to eventually recoup the lost funds.

Keywords: Bad bank, financial stability, stressed assets

1. INTRODUCTION :

Indian industry is expanding rapidly, with new banks and financial institutions opening up every year. India's banking sector is highly diversified, with a wide range of banks and financial institutions serving different segments of the population [1]. As more people enter the middle class, they are increasingly looking for ways to save and invest their money [2]. The banking sector is well-positioned to benefit from this trend, and we expect to see continued growth in the coming years. The banking industry has come a long way in recent years and is now one of the most sophisticated and efficient in the world.

The banks have recently collected a substantial amount of toxic assets as a result of loan defaults by both individual and business borrowers. According to the RBI's financial stability assessment for December 2020, gross non-performing assets might rise to 13.5 per cent by September 2021 and reach 14.8 per cent. This will be a major setback for banks since they will require additional reserves to offset the impact of non-performing assets. A large percentage of NPAs suggests a significant likelihood of credit default, which lowers the system's overall efficiency and effectiveness. Additionally, it drastically decreases the amount of credit that is available, which poses a challenge for both banks and policymakers and stunts the nation's economic expansion [3].

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

The details have been assembled by the secondary method. The study reveals that there has been significant growth of NPA in Indian banking and that's how the idea of a bad bank has been could be a better way to handle bad loans and a better understanding of banking sectors.

3. OBJECTIVES :

- To explore the concept of a bad bank and its overview.

- To glance at the background and evolution of bad banks
- To see its potential benefits and risks, and some real-world examples of bad banks given as opinions of a few authors.

4. WHAT IS A BAD BANK :

A bad bank is a bank that is formed during a financial crisis to purchase non-performing assets, bad loans of regular banks that result from the non-repayment of loans by both individual and company borrowers [4] [5]. The bad bank was meant to assist ordinary banks by taking hazardous assets at prices lesser than the carrying value of existing loans and managing them properly. Most would get reformed, while some might get liquidated, and lastly, the bad bank collects the sum over time. These normal banks will no longer have to worry about problematic loans in the future. Although they are termed banks, they do not operate in the same way as traditional banking systems. A bad bank profits from its operations if it can sell toxic assets or bad loans for a better price than it paid to acquire the toxic assets or poor loans from a bank. However, profit is not its goal of it.

5. EVOLUTION OF BAD BANKS :

The bank was consistently incurring large losses over time to recapitalize its bad assets, poor loans, or non-performing assets. Mellon Bank established Grant Street National Bank (GSNB) and transferred all hazardous assets, defective loans, and non-performing assets to it. The Grant Street National Bank (GSNB) Although they are termed banks, they do not operate in the traditional sense [2] [3]. The Grant Street National Bank (GSNB) began operations in 1988 and closed its doors in July 1995. Mellon Bank's triumph has resulted in the good bank-Bad bank method being adopted in the United States of America (USA) as well as other nations. Taking Grant Street National Bank (GSNB) as inspiration, the United States of America (USA) founded a Resolution trust corporation, an asset management firm. This business is tasked with liquidating hazardous assets declared by banks [6]. The concept of establishing a bad bank in India was first proposed in 2017 when the Macroeconomic Survey of India proposed establishing a public sector asset recovery agency. According to Banking Association which is IBA, a bad bank should start with a capital of around Rs 10000 Cr.

6. BAD BANK ARCHITECTURE :

The IBA has come under fire for its proposed bad bank structure. Under the IBA's plan, bad loans would be transferred to a separate entity, which would then be responsible for managing and resolution of the loans. Critics say that this structure would be expensive and would delay the resolution of bad loans. They further claim that finding purchasers of the poor loans will be tough, as they would be aware that the loans are non-performing. The IBA has defended its proposal, claiming that it is the greatest solution to handle India's bad loan problem It remains to be seen if the RBI would approve the IBA's proposal.

The bad bank will be a two-tiered structure [2],

Tier 1- The Indian government formed an Asset Reconstruction Company (ARC) to buy damaged assets or bad loans from regular banks and provide security receipts. ARC would

keep 15% security revenues by RBI guidelines. The bank will receive 85% of the risk-free income and 15% of the cash.

Tier 2- requires the presence of an Asset Management Company. AMCs must be managed and operated by both public and private entities, including banks.

7. GOOD AND BAD OF THE BAD BANK :

Opinions on the good part of bad banks:

The goal of establishing a bad bank is to address the problem of banks' NPA. They are loans that have been rated as questionable or lost by banks. The focus of the bad bank is to maximize the value of the NPAs so that the banks can recover as much money as possible. Once the NPAs are transferred to the bad bank, the regular banks can focus on their core operations. This will help the banks to improve their performance and become more efficient. In addition, the regular banks will also be able to take on new borrowers and expand their business. Bad banks are specialised institutions that are set up to deal with the problem loans or non-performing assets (NPAs) of another bank. The bad bank is usually a separate entity from the parent bank, and its main goal is to clean up the problem loans so that the parent bank can focus on its core businesses. It typically has special powers and authority, such as the ability to speed up loan recovery and disposal of non-performing assets. This enables them to quickly and efficiently deal with the problem loans, which can help the parent bank to avoid further losses and stabilise its operations. If your bank is struggling with NPAs, setting up a bad bank may be the best solution. With the help of a bad bank, you can clean up your problem loans and get your bank back on track.

Opinions on loopholes or demerits of bad banks:

When some operational judgments made by bad banks fail, the shareholders of the bad banks must pay massive losses. This is because bad banks' assets are often valued lower than their liabilities. The main demerit of bad banks is that they can potentially create moral hazards. This is when people take more risks because they are effectively insulated from the downside. For example, if a bank knows that the government will bail it out if it gets into financial trouble, then it may be more likely to take risks that could lead to financial instability. Another potential problem with bad banks is that they can be used to hide problems. If a bank can transfer its bad loans to a bad bank, then it can make its balance sheet look healthier than it is. This can lead to a false sense of security and could eventually lead to a financial crisis.

8. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS:

The following is a summary of the findings and suggestions for the bad bank:

- 1) The bad bank should be established as a separate legal entity from the parent company.
- 2) The bad bank should have its management team and be run independently from the parent company.
- 3) The bad bank should be given a clean balance sheet and capital structure.
- 4) The bad bank should focus on running off the assets and not on generating profits.
- 5) The parent company should continue to support the bad bank during the run-off period.

9. CONCLUSION :

A bad bank is a financial institution that is created to hold and manage the non-performing assets (NPAs) of another financial institution. The concept of a bad bank was first introduced during the savings and loan crisis in the United States in the 1980s. Bad banks are also known as "NPA sinks" or "troubled asset management companies (TAMCs)".

The main purpose of a bad bank is to remove the NPAs from the balance sheet of the original financial institution so that it can focus on its core business activities. The bad bank is typically a separate legal entity from the original financial institution and is owned by that institution. The bad bank has been controversial. Some argue that it is a necessary tool to help banks during a financial crisis. Others argue that bad banks are not the answer to the problem of struggling banks. They simply shift the problem to another institution, which can eventually lead to even more problems down the road. If a bank is struggling, the best course of action is to work with regulators to find a solution that will benefit all parties involved. It is a way for the government to bail out banks that made bad decisions.

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